

PREPARATION OF 5-CHLORO 7-iodo-8-OXYQUINOLINE

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5-Chloro-7-iodo-8-oxyquinoline has been prepared.

Entero-vioform, 5-chloro-7-iodo-8-oxyquinoline, is an extremely useful drug for the treatment of dysentery. Although a number of firms in Calcutta have put up this drug for sale under various trade names, details of its preparation are not available. According to D.R.P. 117, 767, it is prepared by the action of iodine on 5-chloro 8-oxyquinoline and recently Ghosh, Banerjee and Lasker (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 21, 455) have described a method of the preparation of the chloro compound starting from 2-nitro-4-chlorophenol by Skraup's reaction.

The present investigation was undertaken in the first instance to prepare the chloro-iodo compound from 8-oxyquinoline which also forms the starting material for the preparation of Yatren and Chinosol, by the action of iodine chloride and iodine trichloride. Unfortunately it has been found that iodine monochloride in acetic acid does not react with 8-oxyquinoline, the unchanged starting material being obtained at the end of the operation. Iodine trichloride, which is recognised to be a strong chlorinating agent, unexpectedly gives rise to 5 : 7-di-iodo-8-oxyquinoline in good yield although a small quantity of the expected chloro-iodo compound may be obtained by dilution of the filtrate after the separation of the di-iodo compound (Lasker and Ghosh, *Science & Culture*, 1944, 10, 58). Attempts have been made to prepare 5-chloro derivative by the action of chlorine on 8-oxyquinoline. In acetic acid solution, the main product is 5 : 7-dichloro-8-oxyquinoline (*Ber.*, 1892, 21, 2979). In non-ionising solvents, the chlorination does not proceed to the desired extent as the hydrochloride of the base separates. Attempts have been made to chlorinate the oxyquinoline derivative dissolved in the theoretical quantity of caustic soda so that the hydrochloric acid generated in the reaction would liberate the free base, which being insoluble in water, will be thrown out of solution and thus escape further chlorination. But even in this case the product is 5 : 7-dichloro derivative mixed with unchanged 8-oxyquinoline.

As sulphuryl chloride is known to be an efficient chlorinating agent for phenols, it has been employed in the next series of experiments. In chloroform solution, sulphuryl chloride is found to give a good yield of the monochloro derivative mixed with certain quantity of the dichloro compound. The dichloro compound can be separated easily by evaporating the reaction mixture to dryness and extracting with hot water. The residue gives a m.p. 177° identical with the m.p. of 5 : 7-dichloro-8-oxyquinoline. Contrary to the usual expectation, it is found that the 5-chloro-8-oxyquinoline can be easily obtained from the filtrate by adding sodium acetate and submitting the mixture to steam distillation when the chloro compound passes over smoothly. As sulphuryl chloride can be prepared easily from sulphur dioxide and chlorine, this method of chlorination will prove to be very useful because the same starting material may be used for the preparation of Yatren, Chinosol, Enterovioform and separation by steam distillation will greatly

simplify the process of extracting the desired product as obtained by Skraup's reaction. The iodination of the compound was effected by the method described in D.R.P. 117,767.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of 5-Chloro-8-oxyquinoline.—Sulphuryl chloride (6.7 g.) in chloroform (81g.) was gradually added to the solution of 8-oxyquinoline (7.2 g.) in the same solvent (87 g.) and the solution kept at a temperature 10-15° (time 15-30 minutes). (If the temperature is kept higher the percentage of dichloro derivative is found to be greater). The reaction mixture became warm and fumes of hydrochloric acid were given off. After the reaction was over, the liquid was evaporated to dryness on a water-bath. The residue was boiled with water and filtered. The undissolved residue on crystallisation from acetic acid melts at 177-78° (Hilebrand, *Ber.*, 1888, 21, 2979). The filtrate was treated with sodium acetate when a greenish yellow precipitate separated. This was filtered off and subjected to distillation with steam when a yellow solid passed over, recrystallised from dilute acetic acid it melts at 125-26°, yield 5 g. (Found: N, 7.67, Calc. for C_8H_6ONCl : N, 7.82 per cent).

It is very soluble in alcohol, chloroform, benzene, less soluble in dilute acetic acid and almost insoluble in water.

5-Chloro-7-iodo-8-oxyquinoline.—5-Chloro-8-oxyquinoline (18 g.) was dissolved in potassium hydroxide (6 g.) and water (400 c.c.) with heating. Potassium iodide (8.3 g.) in water (50 c.c.) was added to the solution of chloro-oxyquinoline. While still warm, the liquid was filtered from insoluble impurities, if any, and cooled to room temperature. To the yellow liquid was added a solution of bleaching powder (142 c.c, 5%) with stirring and the solution allowed to stand overnight. The yellowish brown precipitate was filtered off and washed with water several times. The paste was then rubbed in a mortar with sodium thiosulphate to remove free iodine, filtered and washed with water and finally with hydrochloric acid (1%) to remove unreacted chloro-oxyquinoline. Recrystallised from glacial acid, it was obtained as glistening yellow needles, m.p. 178-79°.

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